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CoNSeRT in Researcher's night

On the 30th of September 2022 CoNSeRT's team was happy to present RESCUER at the Researcher's Night 2022, the first physical event after the pandemic that took place in Athens. CoNSeRT's team had the opportunity to present the "Signs of Life" tool to the visitors of the event, as well as to distribute leaflets and invite people to follow our social media channels to stay informed about our latest advancements.

At the same time, RESCUER was presented by the Austrian Red Cross, during their presentation entitled "Research for emergency services – added value for users?" which was held online in the Austrian event.

📍 University Campus II (Ancient Olive Grove)

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